

Counting the number of non-isomorphic top generalized local cohomology modules

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Abstract. Let (R, \mathfrak{m}) be a commutative Noetherian local ring, \mathfrak{a} be a proper ideal of R and M and N be two finitely generated R -modules. In this paper, we give some results in order to count the number of non-isomorphic top generalized local cohomology modules, namely $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)$, where $\dim_R N = n < \infty$ and $\text{pd}_R M = d < \infty$. We prove that this number is equal to $2^{|\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{m}}^{d+n}(M, N))|}$, when $\dim_R R = d + n$ and R is Cohen-Macaulay and complete with respect to the \mathfrak{m} -adic topology.

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1. Introduction

Throughout (R, \mathfrak{m}) denote a commutative Noetherian local ring, \mathfrak{a} and \mathfrak{b} are proper ideals of R and M and N are two finitely generated R -modules. Assume that $\dim_R R = r$, $\dim_R N = n < \infty$, and $\text{pd}_R M = d < \infty$, where $\text{pd}_R M$ denote the projective dimension of M .

Recall that for an R -module L , a prime ideal \mathfrak{p} of R is said to be an attached prime of L if $\mathfrak{p} = \text{Ann}_R(L/K)$ for some submodule K of L . We denote the set of attached primes of L by $\text{Att}_R(L)$. This definition agrees with the usual definition of attached primes if L has a secondary representation, see [1].

In this paper, we are interested in the structure of

$$H_{\mathfrak{a}}^i(M, N) := \varinjlim_n \text{Ext}_R^i(M/\mathfrak{a}^n M, N),$$

the i th generalized local cohomology module with respect to \mathfrak{a} and R -modules M and N , introduced by Herzog [2]. If $M = R$, the definition of generalized local cohomol-

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ogy modules reduces to the notion introduced by Grothendieck [3] of local cohomology modules $H_a^i(N)$.

As we will see in Proposition 2.1, if L is an R -module such that $\dim_R L = n$, $\mathfrak{a} \subseteq \mathfrak{b}$ and $H_a^{d+n}(M, L) \neq 0$, then there is an epimorphism $H_b^{d+n}(M, L) \rightarrow H_a^{d+n}(M, L)$. Based on this result one can ask: when is this epimorphism an isomorphism and when is it not? In other words:

Question 1.1. Let $\text{pd}_R M = d < \infty$ and $\dim_R N = n < \infty$. Is it possible to count the number of non-isomorphic top local cohomology modules $H_a^{d+n}(M, N)$?

The purpose of this paper is to study this question and give a number to this in a particular case. In order to do this, we define the following notation to the sets

$$\text{Assh}(M, N) := \text{Att}_R(H_m^{d+n}(M, N))$$

and

$$\text{Assr}(M, N) := \text{Att}_R(H_m^r(M, N)).$$

Then we prove, on Proposition 2.4, that the number of non-isomorphic top generalized local cohomology modules $H_a^{d+n}(M, N)$ is less than or equal to $2^{|\text{Assh}(M, N)|}$. It is well-known that when $M = R$ and (R, \mathfrak{m}) is complete with respect to the \mathfrak{m} -adic topology, the equality holds (it has been proved in [4, Corollary 2.9]). When M is not necessarily equal to R , we show in Corollary 3.7 that the equality holds, when the ring R is also Cohen-Macaulay.

For conventions of notation, basic results, and terminology not given in this paper, the reader can consult [5] and [6].

2. Some Results

Proposition 2.1. *Let L be an R -module such that $\dim_R L = n$. Suppose $H_a^{d+n}(M, L) \neq 0$ and $\mathfrak{a} \subseteq \mathfrak{b}$. Then there is an epimorphism $H_b^{d+n}(M, L) \rightarrow H_a^{d+n}(M, L)$.*

Proof. We may assume that $\mathfrak{a} \neq \mathfrak{b}$ and choose $x \in \mathfrak{b} \setminus \mathfrak{a}$. By [7, Lemma 3.1], there is an exact sequence

$$H_{\mathfrak{a}+xR}^{d+n}(M, L) \longrightarrow H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, L) \longrightarrow H_{\mathfrak{a}R_x}^{d+n}(M_x, L_x),$$

where L_x is the localization of L at $\{x^i \mid i \geq 0\}$.

Note that $\dim_{R_x}(L_x) < n$ and so $H_{\mathfrak{a}R_x}^{d+n}(M_x, N_x) = 0$. Thus, there is an epimorphism $H_{\mathfrak{a}+xR}^{d+n}(M, N) \longrightarrow H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)$. Now the assertion follows by assuming $\mathfrak{b} = \mathfrak{a} + (x_1, \dots, x_r)$ and applying the argument for finite steps. \square

Theorem 2.2 ([8, Theorem 3.3]). $H_a^{d+n}(M, N) \cong H_b^{d+n}(M, N)$ whenever $Att_R(H_a^{d+n}(M, N)) = Att_R(H_b^{d+n}(M, N))$.

The following Proposition is analogous to Theorem 2.2 but involving the dimension of R and it is worth mentioning. The proof is similar to the Theorem, so we omit it here.

Proposition 2.3. Assume $Att_R(H_a^r(M, N)) \subseteq Ass_R(N)$. In this case, there is an isomorphism $H_a^r(M, N) \cong H_b^r(M, N)$, if $Att_R(H_a^r(M, N)) = Att_R(H_b^r(M, N))$.

Proposition 2.4. The number of non-isomorphic top generalized local cohomology modules $H_a^{d+n}(M, N)$ is less than or equal to $2^{|Assh(M, N)|}$.

Proof. By Proposition 2.1, $Att_R(H_a^{n+d}(M, N)) \subseteq Assh(M, N)$. Then the result follows from the Theorem 2.2. □

Our goal is to know: when does the equality hold?

To what follows, remember: $cd(\mathfrak{a}, M, N) = \sup\{i \mid H_a^i(M, N) \neq 0\}$.

Corollary 2.5. Assume $|Assh(M, N)| = 1$. For any ideal \mathfrak{a} of R , if $cd(\mathfrak{a}, M, N) = d+n$, then $H_a^{d+n}(M, N) \cong H_m^{d+n}(M, N)$. In particular $H_a^{d+n}(M, N)$ is an Artinian R -module.

Proof. Note that $H_a^{d+n}(M, N) \neq 0$, since $cd(\mathfrak{a}, M, N) = d+n$. Moreover, $H_m^{d+n}(M, N) \neq 0$, since $|Assh(M, N)| = 1$ (if $H_m^{d+n}(M, N) = 0$, then $Assh(M, N) = \emptyset$). As the number of non-isomorphic top generalized local cohomology modules $H_a^{d+n}(M, N)$ is not greater than 1, we have the result. □

The next result will be a key point of the main and last result of this section.

Proposition 2.6. Assume that $n \geq 1$ and $T \subset Assh(M, N)$ is a non-empty set. Set $Assh(M, N) \setminus T = \{\mathfrak{q}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{q}_r\}$. Consider the following statements:

- (i) there exists an ideal \mathfrak{a} of R such that $Att_R(H_a^{d+n}(M, N)) = T$;
- (ii) for each $1 \leq i \leq r$, there exists $Q_i \in Supp_R(N)$ such that $\dim_R(R/Q_i) = 1$ with $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_i$ and $\mathfrak{q}_i \subseteq Q_i$.

Then (i) implies (ii).

Proof. As $T = Att_R((H_a^{d+n}(M, N)) \subseteq Att_R((H_a^n(N)))$, by [8, Proposition 2.2 (ii)], then $H_a^n(R/\mathfrak{p}) \neq 0$, for all $\mathfrak{p} \in T$. By the Lichtenbaum-Hartshorne Theorem ([3, 8.2.1]), this is equivalent to say that $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p}$ is a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal, for all $\mathfrak{p} \in T$.

On the other hand, for each $1 \leq i \leq r$, $\mathfrak{q}_i \notin T$, which is equivalent to say that $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i$ is not a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal (again by the Lichtenbaum-Hartshorne Theorem, [3, 8.2.1]). Then, there exists a prime ideal $Q_i \in Supp_R(N)$ such that $\dim_R(R/Q_i) = 1$ and $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i \subseteq Q_i$. In this case, we have $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_i$. □

Now, consider the following sentence:

(i') There exists an ideal \mathfrak{a} of R such that $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)) \subseteq T$.

In the previous hypothesis, we can show (ii) \Rightarrow (i'), where $\mathfrak{a} = \bigcap_{i=1}^r Q_i$, as follows.

Proof. Set $\mathfrak{a} = \bigcap_{i=1}^r Q_i$. For each $1 \leq i \leq r$, $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i \subseteq Q_i$ is equivalent to say that $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i$ is not a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal, hence by the Lichtenbaum-Hartshorne Theorem ([3, 8.2.1]), $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^n(R/Q_i) = 0$. Then $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^n(N)) \subseteq T$. Therefore, $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)) \subseteq T$. \square

Corollary 2.7. *If $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N) \neq 0$, then there is an ideal $\mathfrak{b} \subseteq R$ such that $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N) \cong H_{\mathfrak{b}}^{d+n}(M, N)$ and $\dim_R R/\mathfrak{b} \leq 1$.*

Proof. If $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)) = \text{Assh}(M, N)$, then, by Theorem 2.2, $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N) \cong H_{\mathfrak{m}}^{d+n}(M, N)$.

Otherwise, $d + n \geq 1$ and $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N))$ is a proper subset of $\text{Assh}(M, N)$. Set $\text{Assh}(M, N) \setminus \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)) := \{\mathfrak{q}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{q}_r\}$. By the proof of Proposition 2.6, for each $1 \leq i \leq r$, there exists $Q_i \in \text{Supp}_R(M)$ with $\dim_R (R/Q_i) = 1$ such that $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)) = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{b}}^{d+n}(M, N))$, where $\mathfrak{b} = \bigcap_{i=1}^r Q_i$. Again, by Theorem 2.2, $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N) \cong H_{\mathfrak{b}}^{d+n}(M, N)$. Since $\dim_R R/\mathfrak{m} = 0$ and $\dim_R R/\mathfrak{b} = 1$, we have the result. \square

3. The Cohen-Macaulay case

Recall that a finitely generated R -module M is a *Cohen-Macaulay module* if $\text{depth } M = \dim_R M$. If R itself is a Cohen-Macaulay module, then it is called a *Cohen-Macaulay ring*. A *maximal Cohen-Macaulay module* is a Cohen-Macaulay module M such that $\dim_R M = \dim_R R$. For more information about Cohen-Macaulay rings and modules the reader can see the book of Bruns-Herzog [5].

From now on, we assume that (R, \mathfrak{m}) is a commutative Noetherian Cohen-Macaulay local ring, complete with respect to the \mathfrak{m} -adic topology, such that $\dim_R R = r$. Let \mathfrak{a} and \mathfrak{b} be ideals of R . We also assume that M and N are two finitely generated R -modules such that $\text{pd}_R M = d < \infty$ and $\dim_R N = n < \infty$.

Note that $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^r(M, N)$ is an Artinian R -module for all R -ideal \mathfrak{a} and

$$\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^r(M, N)) = \{\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Supp}_R(N) \cap \text{Ass}_R(M) \mid \dim_R (R/\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p}) = 0\},$$

by [7, Theorems 3.8 and 3.9], since R is complete with respect to the \mathfrak{m} -adic topology.

Proposition 3.1. Assume $r \geq 1$ and T is a proper non-empty subset of $\text{Assr}(M, N)$. Set $\text{Assr}(M, N) \setminus T = \{\mathfrak{q}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{q}_s\}$. The following statements are equivalent:

- (i) There exists an ideal \mathfrak{a} of R such that $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^r(M, N)) = T$;
- (ii) For each $1 \leq i \leq s$, there exists $Q_i \in \text{Supp}_R(N)$ such that $\dim_R(R/Q_i) = 1$ with $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_i$ and $\mathfrak{q}_i \subseteq Q_i$.

Where $\mathfrak{a} = \bigcap_{i=1}^s Q_i$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Since

$$T = \{\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Supp}_R(N) \cap \text{Assr}(M) \mid \dim_R(R/\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p}) = 0\} \neq \emptyset,$$

$\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p}$ is a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal, for all $\mathfrak{p} \in T$. On the other hand, by the same argument, $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i$ is not a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal, since $\mathfrak{q}_i \notin T$, for all $1 \leq i \leq s$. Then there exists $Q_i \in \text{Supp}_R(N)$ such that $\dim_R(R/Q_i) = 1$ and $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i \subseteq Q_i$. Therefore, $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_i$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Set $\mathfrak{a} = \bigcap_{i=1}^s Q_i$. For all $1 \leq i \leq s$, $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i \subseteq Q_i$, then $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{q}_i$ is not a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal. Thus, $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^r(M, N)) \subseteq T$.

On the other hand, take $\mathfrak{p} \in T \subseteq \text{Assr}(M, N) = \text{Supp}_R(N) \cap \text{Assr}(M)$ and let $Q \in \text{Supp}_R(N)$ such that $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p} \subseteq Q$. Then there exists $i \in \{1, \dots, s\}$ such that $Q_i \subseteq Q$. Notice that $\mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_i$, since $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_i$, then $Q_i \neq Q$. Thus, $Q = \mathfrak{m}$. So $\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p}$ is a \mathfrak{m} -primary ideal then $\dim_R(R/\mathfrak{a} + \mathfrak{p}) = 0$. Therefore, $\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^r(M, N))$. \square

Corollary 3.2. If $r = 1$, then any subset of $\text{Assr}(M, N)$ is equal to $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^1(M, N))$, for some ideal \mathfrak{a} of R .

Proof. In the notation of the Proposition 3.1, it is enough to take $Q_i = \mathfrak{q}_i$, for $i = 1, \dots, s$. \square

Lemma 3.3. Assume $r \geq 2$. Let $\mathfrak{a}_1, \mathfrak{a}_2$ be ideals of R . Then there exists an ideal \mathfrak{b} of R such that $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{b}}^r(M, N)) = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}_1}^r(M, N)) \cap \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}_2}^r(M, N))$.

Proof. Consider $T_1 = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}_1}^r(M, N))$ and $T_2 = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}_2}^r(M, N))$. Suppose $T_1 \cap T_2$ is a non-empty proper subset of $\text{Assr}(M, N)$. Let $\mathfrak{q} \in \text{Assr}(M, N) \setminus (T_1 \cap T_2) = (\text{Assr}(M, N) \setminus T_1) \cup (\text{Assr}(M, N) \setminus T_2)$. By Proposition 3.1, there exists $Q \in \text{Supp}_R(N)$ such that $\dim_R(R/Q) = 1$ with $\mathfrak{q} \subseteq Q$ and $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T_1} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q$ or $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T_2} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q$. Thus, there exists Q satisfying the above conditions such that $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T_1 \cap T_2} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q$. Therefore, again by Proposition 3.1, there exists an ideal \mathfrak{b} of R such that $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{b}}^r(M, N)) = T_1 \cap T_2$. \square

Lemma 3.4. Assume $r = d + n \geq 2$. Let T be a non-empty subset of $\text{Assr}(M, N) = \text{Assh}(M, N)$ and $T' = \text{Assh}(M, N) \setminus T = \{\mathfrak{q}\}$. If $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq \bigcap_{\mathfrak{b} \in \text{Assh}(M, R/\mathfrak{p})} \mathfrak{b}$,

then there exists a prime ideal $Q \in \text{Supp}_R(N)$ such that $\dim_R(R/Q) = 1$ and $\text{Att}_R(H_Q^{d+n}(M, N)) = T$.

Proof. First note that $\dim_R R/\mathfrak{q} = d + n = r$, since $\mathfrak{q} \in T' \subset \text{Assh}(M, N)$. We prove by induction in j ($0 \leq j \leq r - 1$) that there exists a chain of prime ideals $Q_0 \subset Q_1 \subset \dots \subset Q_j \subset \mathfrak{m}$ such that $Q_0 \in \text{Assh}(M, R/\mathfrak{q})$, $\dim_R(R/Q_j) = r - j$ and $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_j$.

Now, note that there exists $Q_0 \in \text{Assh}(M, R/\mathfrak{q})$ such that $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_0$, since $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq \bigcap_{\mathfrak{b} \in \text{Assh}(M, R/\mathfrak{q})} \mathfrak{b}$, and $\dim_R(R/Q_0) = \dim_R R/\mathfrak{q} = r$.

Let $0 < j \leq r - 1$ and suppose we already prove the existence of the chain of prime ideals $Q_0 \subset Q_1 \subset \dots \subset Q_{j-1}$ such that $Q_0 \in \text{Assh}(M, R/\mathfrak{q})$, $\dim_R(R/Q_j) = r - (j - 1)$ and $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_{j-1}$. Note that $r - j + 1 \geq 2$, since $r - j - 1 \geq 0$. Thus, the set

$$V = \{ \mathfrak{q} \in \text{Supp}_R(N) \mid Q_{j-1} \subset \mathfrak{q} \subset \mathfrak{q}' \subset \mathfrak{m}, \dim_R R/\mathfrak{q} = r - j, \\ \mathfrak{q}' \in \text{Spec}(R), \dim_R R/\mathfrak{q}' = r - j - 1 \}$$

is non-empty and therefore, by Ratliff's weak existence Theorem ([6, Theorem 31.2]), is infinite.

Since $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_{j-1}$, we have that $Q_{j-1} \subset Q_{j-1} + \bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p}$. If $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \subseteq \mathfrak{q}$ for $\mathfrak{q} \in V$, then \mathfrak{q} is a minimal prime ideal of $Q_{j-1} + \bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p}$. Thus, there is $Q_j \in V$ such that $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq Q_j$, since V is an infinite set and the amount of minimal primes of $Q_{j-1} + \bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p}$ is finite. Therefore, taking $Q := Q_{r-1}$, by Proposition 3.1, the result is as follows. □

Corollary 3.5. *Assume $r = d + n \geq 2$. If $T \subseteq \text{Assh}(M, N)$ is non-empty and $T' = \text{Assh}(M, N) \setminus T = \{ \mathfrak{q} \}$, then there is an ideal \mathfrak{a} of R such that $\text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)) = T$.*

Proof. Define, for any prime ideal $\mathfrak{b} \in \text{Spec}(R)$,

$$\text{ht}_N(\mathfrak{b}) = \inf \{ s \mid P_0 \subseteq P_1 \subseteq \dots \subseteq P_s \subseteq \mathfrak{b}, \text{ with } P_i \in \text{Supp}_R(N) \}.$$

Note that $\text{ht}_N(\mathfrak{q}) = 0$, since $\mathfrak{q} \in \text{Ass}_R(N) \subseteq \text{Supp}_R(N)$. Thus $\bigcap_{\mathfrak{p} \in T} \mathfrak{p} \not\subseteq \mathfrak{q} \subseteq \bigcap_{\mathfrak{b} \in \text{Assh}(M, R/\mathfrak{p})} \mathfrak{b}$. Therefore, by Lemma 3.4, the result follows. □

Now we are able to show the main result of this section.

Theorem 3.6. *Assume $r = d + n$. If $T \subseteq \text{Assh}(M, N)$, then there exists an ideal \mathfrak{a} of R such that $T = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N))$.*

Proof. By Corollary 3.2, we may assume $r \geq 2$ and T is a non-empty proper subset of $\text{Assh}(M, N)$. Let $T = \{\mathfrak{p}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{p}_t\}$ and $\text{Assh}(M, N) \setminus T = \{\mathfrak{p}_{t+1}, \dots, \mathfrak{p}_{t+s}\}$. We use induction over s . For $s = 1$, the result holds by Corollary 3.5.

Suppose that $s > 1$ and the result holds for the case $s - 1$. Consider $T_1 = \{\mathfrak{p}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{p}_t, \mathfrak{p}_{t+1}\}$ and $T_2 = \{\mathfrak{p}_1, \dots, \mathfrak{p}_t, \mathfrak{p}_{t+2}\}$. By induction, there exists ideals \mathfrak{a}_1 and \mathfrak{a}_2 of R such that $T_1 = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}_1}^{d+n}(M, N))$ and $T_2 = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}_2}^{d+n}(M, N))$. Therefore, by Lemma 3.3, there exists an ideal \mathfrak{a} of R such that $T = T_1 \cap T_2 = \text{Att}_R(H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N))$. \square

As an immediate consequence of Theorem 3.6, we have our main result, which counts the number of non-isomorphic top generalized local cohomology modules.

Corollary 3.7. *The number of non-isomorphic top local cohomology modules $H_{\mathfrak{a}}^{d+n}(M, N)$ is equal to $2^{|\text{Assh}(M, N)|}$, when $r = d + n$.*

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